

REECO-SOIL

REECO-SOIL Systematic Literature Review Search Strategy

Project Acronym: REECO-SOIL

Project Title: Regenerative Retrofitting Via Ecologically Active Soil Structures

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1 Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Review Literature Search (PRISMA-S)

1.1 Introduction

The quality of a systematic literature review heavily relies on the search strategy implemented for the information retrieval process. Nevertheless, search strategies are commonly not adequately reported. This document presents the search strategy adopted with the aim of exploring what the current materials (soil types), methods (application techniques), and biological components (plant species) are used in the literature for integrating ecologically active soils into building retrofitting strategies. It follows the PRISMA-S [1] checklist.

1.2 Search strategy

The recommended items to address in a search strategy according to the PRISMA-S checklist are presented in Table 1, Table 2, Table 3 and Table 4. This search strategy has been developed and documented to ensure transparency of the systematic review and facilitate its reproducibility.

Table 1. Information sources and methods.

Database name:	The following electronic databases were searched: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scopus (Elsevier). • Web of Science Core Collection (Clarivate).
Multi-database searching:	No multi-database platforms were used; each database was searched individually.
Study registries:	None. This review focuses on published literature, not clinical or project trial registries.
Online resources and browsing:	Design and construction websites such as Designboom, Dezeen, The Architects' Journal, and New Civil Engineering were searched for real-world project case studies on 3D printing with soil.
Citation searching:	Only backward citation searching was conducted (i.e., screening reference lists of included studies). No forward citation searching was performed.
Contacts:	No further details were searched by directly contacting authors, experts, manufacturers, or others.
Other methods:	No other methods were used.

Table 2. Search strategies.

Full search strategy:	Three different search queries were run implementing the specified eligibility criteria and combining the various keywords of interest identified. The full search queries were: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Scopus: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. TITLE-ABS-KEY(("ecologic* soil" OR "bioactiv* soil" OR "engineer* soil" OR "earthen" OR "earthen construction" OR "soil-based material*" OR clay) AND (retrofit* OR "building envelope" OR "facade retrofit*" OR "building refurbish*" OR "thermal upgrad*")) AND PUBYEAR > 1999 AND PUBYEAR < 2026 AND (LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"ENGI") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"MATE") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"ENVI") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"ENER")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE,"ar") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE,"cp") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE,"ch") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE,"bk")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE,"English")). b. TITLE-ABS-KEY (("soil-based material*" OR "bioactiv* soil" OR "living soil" OR "engineer* soil" OR clay OR "earthen*" OR "earthen construction") AND ("3D print*" OR "additive manufactur*" OR extrus* OR spray* OR "robotic extrus*" OR "digital fabricat*") AND (retrofit* OR "thermal insulat*" OR "building refurbish*")) AND PUBYEAR > 1999 AND PUBYEAR < 2026 AND (LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA , "MATE") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA , "ENGI") OR
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	<p>LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA , "ENVI") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA , "ENER")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "cp") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ch")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English")).</p> <p>c. TITLE-ABS-KEY (("soil" OR "engineer* substrate*" OR "bioactiv* soil" OR "earthen" OR "earthen construction") AND ("plant* growth" OR "green infrastructur*" OR "vegetat* surface*" OR "living facade*" OR "urban green*" OR "vertical garden*" OR "plant-support* material*") AND retrofit*) AND PUBYEAR > 2000 AND PUBYEAR < 2025 AND (LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA , "ENVI") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA , "ENGI") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA , "ENER")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "cp") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ch")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English")).</p> <p>2. Web of Science:</p> <p>a. TS=(("ecologic* soil" OR "bioactiv* soil" OR "engineer* soil" OR "earthen" OR "earthen construction" OR "soil-based material*" OR clay) AND (retrofit* OR "building envelope" OR "facade retrofit*" OR "building refurbish*" OR "thermal upgrad*")) AND PY=(2000-2025).</p> <p>b. TS=(("soil-based material*" OR "bioactiv* soil" OR "living soil" OR "engineer* soil" OR clay OR "earthen*" OR "earthen construction") AND ("3D print*" OR "additive manufactur*" OR extrus* OR spray* OR "robotic extrus*" OR "digital fabricat*")) AND (retrofit* OR "thermal insulat*" OR "building refurbish*")) AND PY=(2000-2025).</p> <p>c. TS=(("soil" OR "engineer* substrate*" OR "bioactiv* soil" OR "earthen*" OR "earthen construction") AND ("plant* growth" OR "green infrastructur*" OR "vegetat* surface*" OR "living facade*" OR "urban green*" OR "vertical garden*" OR "plant-support* material*") AND retrofit*) AND PY=(2000-2025).</p>
Limits and restrictions:	The search was limited to the search fields of title, abstract and keywords in Scopus, and to the topic field (which searches <i>title, abstract, and keywords</i>) in Web of Science.
Search filters:	<p>The following filters were applied:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scopus: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Years: 2000-2025. ○ Subject areas: Engineering, Materials Science, Environmental Science, and Energy. ○ Document types: Article, Conference Paper, Book Chapters, or Book. ○ Language: English. • Web of Science: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Years: 2000-2025. ○ Document types: Article, Proceeding Paper, Book Chapter. ○ WoS Categories: Engineering Civil, Construction Building Technology, Materials Science Multidisciplinary, Engineering Environmental, Engineering Multidisciplinary, Environmental Sciences. ○ Language: English.
Prior work:	The search strategy adopted has been created specifically for this systematic review. No search strategies from previous literature reviews have been adopted.
Updates:	No update method will be used (although both Scopus and Web of Science allow the use of search alerts) as the final manuscript will be completed shortly after the search had been performed.
Dates of searchers:	The search was conducted on 30/04/2025.

Table 3. Peer review.

Peer review:	The search strategy document will be made available online along with the systematic review protocol in the OSF website of the project [2]. Both documents are available to receive open peer reviews under the Resources tab of the project Registry website [3].
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Table 4. Managing records.

Total records:	The total records found will be reported in accordance to the PRISMA 2020 flow
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diagram for systematic reviews [4]. The number of records identified with each of the search queries reported were:

1. Scopus (648):
 - a. 569.
 - b. 39.
 - c. 40.
2. Web of Science (332):
 - a. 288.
 - b. 25.
 - c. 19.

A FAIR bibliographic database has been created with all the records identified at this stage [5].

Deduplication:

The deduplication process was conducted manually filtering duplicate titles for each database separately. The number of records for each one of the search queries after deduplications were:

1. Scopus (635):
 - a. 563.
 - b. 35.
 - c. 37.
2. Web of Science (325):
 - a. 288.
 - b. 21.
 - c. 16.

After manually cross filtering duplicate records between both databases 240 duplicated values were found and removed. 720 records remained.

References

1. Rethlefsen, M.L., et al., *PRISMA-S: an extension to the PRISMA Statement for Reporting Literature Searches in Systematic Reviews*. *Systematic Reviews*, 2021. **10**(1): p. 39. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13643-020-01542-z>.
2. Jiménez Rios, A., J. Calabria-Holley, and F.J. Castilla Pascual, *Regenerative Retrofitting Via Ecologically Active Soil Structures (Reeco-Soil) Project*. OSF, 2025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/FGBYW>.
3. Jiménez Rios, A., J. Calabria-Holley, and F.J. Castilla Pascual, *Regenerative Retrofitting Via Ecologically Active Soil Structures (Reeco-Soil) Registry*. OSF Registries, 2025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/9PGZ4>.
4. Page, M.J., et al., *The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews*. *BMJ*, 2021. **372**: p. n71. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.n71>.
5. Jiménez Rios, A., J. Calabria-Holley, and F.J. Castilla Pascual, *Bibliographic Dataset for the Regenerative Retrofitting Via Ecologically Active Soil Structures (Reeco-Soil) Research Project*. 2025. Zenodo. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15318914>.

Annex A

Table 5. History of changes.

Version	Publication date	Change
1.0	07/05/2025	Initial version.

